

EIDIP framework predicted wide binary stars anomaly as long-range Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 anomaly

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In this vast universe, what is the chance that one predicted a gravitational anomaly at certain astronomical distance, and then the anomaly is observed at that distance? In this short communication paper, I explain the observed Wide binary stars anomaly (WBSA) was *predicted* by EIDIP (Energy-space interdomain interaction potential) GUT framework, and that the WBSA is the long-range extension of the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration (PSAA) anomalies; i.e., they are produced by the same type of gravitational interaction potential named EIDIP that can be described by a *single parameter non-linear* function (Slide 4-5 of [1], <https://zenodo.org/record/5495929#.ZEITpM7MJhH>). The Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 anomalies are produced by short-range angular EIDIP effect, whereas the wide binary stars anomaly is produced by long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effect. Furthermore, the WBSA's galactic distance near $[2000]_{AU}$ was predicted by the EIDIP framework (Fig 50 of [2], <https://zenodo.org/uploads/3471904>, 2018). The aforementioned gravitational interaction potential EIDIP has a 7+ Sigma confidence based on 13+ phenological tests (section 2 of [1]) between well accepted empirical data sets and Matlab simulations [3] (<https://zenodo.org/records/3471963#.ZEIToc7MJhH>, 2019). The objectivity/deterministic of Matlab simulations are inarguable.

Keywords: EIDIP, GUT, TOE, MOG, modified gravity, Wide binary star anomaly, Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 anomaly.

I. INTRODUCTION

This short paper is meant to communicate that the observed wide binary stars anomaly (WBSA) in the Gaia DR3 data [4] (2024) was *predicted* by the EIDIP (Energy-space interdomain interaction potential) framework as the long-range extension of the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration (PSAA) anomalies (VI.C of [2], 2018). In this vast universe, what is the chance that one predicted a gravitational anomaly at certain astronomical distance, and then the anomaly is observed at that distance?

The EIDIP P_E can be described by a *single parameter non-linear* function (Slide 4-5, [1]). The EIDIP effects have these strange behaviors shown in FIG. 1: *turbulent* in short-range, aka near singularity turbulent EIDIP effect (NSTEE) region, and *ruly* in long-range, aka conformal region; e.g., the angular EIDIP effect $P_r \equiv rP_E$ (red curve, FIG. 1) is asymptotic in the NSTEE region, and settle-to-constant in the conformal region. The long-range settle-to-constant of angular EIDIP effect underlying the PSAA would surpass the gravity near $[2859]_{AU}$ (FIG. 3, also slide 21, [1]) such that it can produce the observed wide binary stars' gravitational anomaly near and beyond this distance as shown in (FIG. 8).

Based on the PSAA EIDIP effect phenological test (EPT) (VI.C of [2], 2018), the EIDIP framework *predicted* that, for a rotational astronomical interaction system with center object mass of Sun, the *settle-to-constant* angular EIDIP effect can produce gravitational anomalies near and beyond distance $[2859]_{AU}$ where gravity strength nears $[1.088e - 9]_{m_s^{-2}}$ and below (FIG. 3). This prediction fits the observed gravitational wide binary stars (WBSA) anomalies (FIG. 8) that “occur at low

acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$ or for a sky-projected separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ for typical binaries with total masses of $\sim(0.5-2)$ Sun mass,... the magnitude and trend of the anomaly matched well the predictions of MOND-type modified gravity” [4].

I.e., the wide binary stars anomalies (WBSA) and the Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies (PSAA) are produced by the long-range angular EIDIP effect $P_r \equiv rP_E$ (red curve, FIG. 1; blue curve, FIG. 2). Note that the long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects can also provide theoretical base for those ad hoc MOND and modified gravity (MOG) models.

The gravitational interactions operate at various scale or energy domain (E-domain), each with its own domain spatial unit (dsu).¹ E.g., the subatomic angular EIDIP P_r produced the strong interaction's asymptotic and settle-to-constant confinement behaviors (slide 19, [1]); whereas the astronomical angular EIDIP in the NSTEE region produce the asymptotic Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies (FIG. 2).

¹ Refer to slide 49 of [1]; e.g., both the PSAA and WBSA operate at the second order expansive E-domain (Dx2) with $[1]_{Dx2}^{dsu} = [(32\pi)^2 c / 2]_m$; the strong interaction operates at the 2.5th order contractive E-

domain (Dc2.5) with $[1]_{Dc2.5}^{dsu} = [R_0 / (32\pi)^{2.5}]_m$ where $R_0 \cong 1 / (32\pi c)$ is a defined unitless constant and c is the speed of light in the SI unit.

FIG. 1. (Color online) Short-range near singularity turbulent EIDIP effects (NTEE) and long-range ruly (conformal) EIDIP effects behaviors example figure: rP_r' (blue) and $P_d r^2$ (green) and P_r (red), normalized in domain spatial unit (dsu).²

In this paper, the session II recaps the PSAA EIDIP effect phenological test (EEPT) of [2] and session III contains a preliminary WBSA EIDIP effect phenological test. The session IV presents conclusion and discussion. For detail EIDIP GUT framework, refer to EIDIP GUT framework paper [2] (2018) and the updated slide doc [1] (2021) which shows that the existence of EIDIP has a 7+ Sigma confidence based on 13+ phonological tests (section 2 of [1]) between well accepted empirical data sets and Matlab simulations [3] (2019). The objectivity/deterministic of Matlab simulations is inarguable.

II. SHORT-RANGE ANGULAR EIDIP EFFECT PRODUCED PIONEER SPACECRAFT 10/11 ANOMALIES

The Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft sunward acceleration (PSAA) is produced by an angular EIDIP effect induced acceleration (APA, G_{APA}).

The sun rotates once approximately every 27 days; although slow, the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft and rotating sun make up rotational interaction systems that can produce angular EIDIP effects. Because of G_{APA} 's asymptotic behavior, the meter-range sunward G_{APA} is much lower than gravity and neglectable. However, with the massive sun mass, the sunward G_{APA} becomes noticeable at inter-planetary distances. Because Newtonian gravity model does not account for EIDIP effects, the G_{APA} induced sunward accelerations appear as anomalies.

With the EIDIP function's only parameter, named interdomain transfer factor, $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, a distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dx2} = [(32\pi)^2 c/2]_m$, and a magnitude formula

$$G_{APA}^{PSAA} = P_r M_{\odot} H_{kg}^0 2_{Dc2}^2 1_{Dx2},^3 \quad (1)$$

with $M_{\odot} = [1.98855 \pm 0.00025 \times 10^{30}]_{\text{kg}}$ as Sun mass in kilograms [5], the G_{APA}^{PSAA} curve (blue curve, FIG. 2) traces *both* Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly datasets of [6]

Although the magnitude of EIDIP is proportional to the mass product of both bodies as the gravity, only the object in the origin (Sun mass in this case) is needed in this centripetal force calculation.

² $P_d \equiv d(P_E)/dr$, $P_r \equiv rP_E$, $P_r' \equiv d(P_r)/dr$ with radius r .

³ $H_{kg}^0 = [2.24e - 25]_{kg}$ is the interaction defect mass unit and is within the measured Higgs boson mass range; $1_{Dx2} = (32\pi)^2 c/2$, $1_{Dc2} = R_0/(32\pi)^2$, $R_0 \equiv 1/(32\pi c)$.

⁴ Note that the additional $1e-10$ magnitude factor from Equ (1) is needed to fit the Y-axis unit $1e-13 \text{ km/sec}^2$.

⁵ The EIDIP function is produced by "convolution" of two gravitational potential, named MWEP (matter warped E-space potential) (slide 4, [1]), that have discontinuity and jump singularities. In Fourier

FIG. 2. (Color online) Short-range G_{APA} ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) induced PSAA curve (blue) traces *both* Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration empirical data figure of [6]: magenta dashed lines show the PSAA curve acme location in AU (astronomical units) and magnitude.⁴

The single parameter nonlinear EIDIP function has high number of high order terms in polynomial expansion such that the EIDIP effect function is unlikely to fit unrelated physical phenomena by accident.⁵ Because that, the EIDIP effects induced physical phenomena cannot be fully described by conventional perturbative methods or models. However, because some long range EIDIP effects have settling to constant behavior such that they can be approximated by ad hoc MOND or MOG (modified gravity) type formula; i.e., the settle-to-constant angular EIDIP can be the theoretical base for MOND and MOG.

Note that the thermal recoil force (TRF) based model put forth by [7], which is often touted as the source of PSAA, is not the source of PSAA because:

- (1) Based on figure 4 of [7], the estimated Jaccard similarity coefficient between the TRF model produced data and empirical Doppler residual data is approximately 20% which indicates inequality between the TRF model and empirical data;
- (2) The TRF model data is slowly descending with distance of which the behavior cannot explain the steep-ascending segment of the newer Pioneer 11 spacecraft's data; in comparison, the G_{APA} -PSAA curve fits both Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's data including the steep-ascending segment.

A. Long-range G_{APA}^{PSAA} crossover gravity near 2859 AU and produced WIDE BINARY STAR anomaly

Despite the meter-range G_{APA}^{PSAA} being much weaker than

transform, a magnitude jump in a source signal would result an infinite frequency term post Fourier transformation. Form which, one can derive that the resulted EIDIP function would also have has high number of high order terms. In order to fit physical phenomena, all those high order terms of EIDIP function would also need to be "match" to the Fourier components of physical phenomena. Hence, I argue that it is unlikely that the EIDIP effects can fit unrelated physical phenomena by accident.

gravity, the long-range settle-to-constant $G_{APA}^{PSAA} \propto r^0$ and inverse distance square gravitational acceleration $G_N \propto r^{-2}$ can reach equilibrium at some interstellar distances. Based on Matlab simulation, the G_{APA}^{PSAA} crossover gravity approximately at $[2859]_{AU}$ with strength of $[1.088e - 9]_{m_s^{-2}}$ and become dominant pass that distance (FIG. 3).

This prediction fits the gravitational wide binary stars (WBSA) anomalies (FIG. 8) that “occur at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$ or for a sky-projected separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ for typical binaries with total masses of $\sim(0.5-2)$ Sun mass, ...the magnitude and trend of the anomaly matched well the predictions of MOND-type modified gravity” [4].

FIG. 3. Long range G_{APA}^{PSAA} induced centripetal acceleration (blue line) surpass gravity induced centripetal acceleration (green line) at $[2859]_{AU}$ figure.

III. LONG-RANGE ANGULAR EIDIP EFFECT PRODUCED WIDE BINARY STAR GRAVITATIONAL ANOMALIES

Wide binary stars selected from Gaia data release 3 has revealed a gravitational anomaly that at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$ or for a sky-projected separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ for typical binaries with total masses of $\sim(0.5-2)$ Sun mass, and that the magnitude and trend of the anomaly matched well the predictions of MOND-type modified gravity [4].

Note that the strength of EIDIP effects is proportional the masses of involved bodies as the Newtonian gravity, and that the EIDIP effects induced centripetal acceleration are proportional the center body’s mass as Newtonian gravity. Hence, the aforementioned crossover distance is not affected by the massed of both bodies although the gravity strength may differ at this crossover distance. Hence, the EIDIP framework predicted crossover distance $[2859]_{AU}$ is applicable to the wide binary stars anomaly distance and aligned with the “at separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ ”.

Furthermore, because that the wide binary stars’ mass used in [4] is in the range of $\sim(0.5-2)$ Sun mass, and that the only the center mass is needed for the centripetal acceleration calculations, the EIDIP framework predicted

Newtonian gravity crossover strength of $[1.088e - 9]_{m_s^{-2}}$ is also applicable and aligned with the observed wide binary stars anomaly at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$.

I.e., the EIDIP framework predicted Newtonian gravity strength at crossover distance $[1.088 \times 10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$ for the PSAA fit the observed WBSA’s location and gravity strength “at separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ and at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{m_s^{-2}}$ ” [4].

FIG. 4 depicts the centripetal accelerations sources underlying the PSAA near G_{APA}^{PSAA} crossover distance: angular EIDIP effect G_{APA}^{PSAA} (blue line), gravity G_N (green line), and total $G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$ (dot-dashed red line); the vertical dashed line shows the crossover distance $[2859]_{AU}$.

FIG. 4. Long range G_{APA}^{PSAA} induced centripetal acceleration (blue line), gravity induced centripetal acceleration (green line), and total centripetal acceleration ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) (red dotted line) without inclination angle adjustment figure.

Note that in the G_{APA}^{PSAA} dominated region (e.g., APA dominated region in FIG. 3 and FIG. 4), the constructed center star mass solely based on Newtonian gravity can be way off (higher than actual) because most of the observed centripetal acceleration in this region would be produced by the settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects, a type of omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIA) which is also a likely source of dark matter.

Because that only the center mass affects the centripetal acceleration calculation, the angular EIDIP effect calculated from PSAA with adjusted 1.5x Sun mass as center mass is applicable to the wide binary star’s centripetal acceleration calculation.

FIG. 5 depicts the gravity (G_N , blue line) and total ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$, red curve) induced centripetal acceleration calculated with center star mass of 1.5x Sun mass. The Y-axis is the expected to observed centripetal acceleration \log -value in linear-scale, whereas the X-axis is the gravity only centripetal acceleration in \log -scale.

FIG. 5. Total centripetal acceleration ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) (red line) and gravity induced centripetal acceleration G_N (blue line), star to Sun mass factor = 1.5 for Sun and Pioneer spacecraft like system figure.

FIG. 6. depicts the log-value deviation between total and gravity only acceleration $\log_{10}(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ calculated with center star mass of 1.5x Sun mass. The Y-axis is the log-deviation in linear-scale, whereas the X-axis is the gravity only centripetal acceleration in log-scale.

FIG. 6. $\log_{10}(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ (blue line) for Sun and Pioneer spacecraft like system figure.

FIG. 7 is reproduced from figure 7 of [4] to illustrate the parameters (x_0 , Δ_{\perp}) and construed data used in FIG. 8 (reproduced from the left subfigure of figure 8 of [4])⁶. In FIG. 8, the upper panel is overlaid with the total acceleration $G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$ (red dashed line) and G_N (dashed blue line) of FIG. 5; whereas the lower panel is overlaid with $\log_{10}(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ (dotted blue line) of FIG. 6. (refer to session III.A for overlay method details)

FIG. 8 shows that the EIDIP effect induced centripetal acceleration behaves in this region are within the binned data range in figure 8 of [4].

⁶ FIG. 8 is reproduced from the left subfigure of figure 8 of [4]; the upper panel depicts the observed centripetal acceleration (red line) and expected Newtonian centripetal acceleration G_N (black sloped straight line) (refer to figure 7 of [4] for detailed Δ_{\perp} definition). The lower panel

Because that the x is a projected centripetal acceleration and Δ_{\perp} is a distance on log-log plane as shown in FIG. 7, and that they differ from the X and Y axes' units of overlay figures FIG. 5 and FIG. 6, some deviations between the mean curve of binned data in original figure and EIDIP effect curves are expected.

Despite the Y-unit difference, the fact that the curves of FIG. 5 can be scaled to map to the upper subfigure of [4] indicates that the constructed $\langle \Delta_{\perp} \rangle_{obs}$ is indeed related to the total ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) induced centripetal acceleration. The 7+ Sigma of EIDIP's existence further affirms this assertion.

Note that in FIG. 8, the EIDIP framework predicts that the $\log_{10}(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ (dotted blue line) toward lower acceleration region would increase and not saturate as predicted by AQUAL (purple line) for circular orbits with the Milky Way external field.

FIG. 7 (Reproduce from figure 7 of [4]) MC-realized (Monte Carlo deprojected 3D separation and relative velocity distributions) of the 2463 pure binaries in the acceleration plane defined in in [8] (Chae 2023) figure. The quantity $g_N \equiv GM_{tot}/r^2$ is the Newtonian gravitational acceleration between the two stars and $g \equiv v^2/r$ is an empirical kinematic acceleration, where r and v are the deprojected 3D separation and relative velocity. The left panel shows a Newton-predicted distribution, while the right panel shows a distribution from Gaia measurements from one MC realization. The big dots indicate the medians in the orthogonal bins indicated by the magenta dotted lines. The orthogonal deviation Δ_{\perp} of a point from the diagonal line is indicated in the inset of the upper left panel. The bottom panels show the medians of Δ_{\perp} in the bins. In the right panels, the Gaia medians are compared with the Newtonian medians.

depicts the deviation between the observed and Newtonian centripetal accelerations.

FIG. 8 Top panel: Total centripetal acceleration ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) (red dashed line), gravity G_N (blue dashed line) of FIG. 5, and the deviation between the log value of $\log_{10}(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ (dotted blue line) overlaid on the left subfigure of figure 8 of [4].⁷

If one agrees to the observation alignment of FIG. 4, one should also agree to the $(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N)/G_N$ curve of FIG. 9. This is because 1) FIG. 4 aligns with the WBSA’s occurrence at separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ which aligns with the X-axis range and at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{ms^{-2}}$ which aligns with the long range value G_{APA}^{PSAA} , 2) the trend of the anomaly matched well the predictions of MOND-type (ad hoc constant acceleration) modified gravity which aligns with the settle-to-constant long range G_{APA}^{PSAA} , 3) the $(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N)/G_N$ shown in FIG. 9 is a logical derivation or just a different presentation of FIG. 4.

FIG. 9 shows the $(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N)/G_N = 4.07$ at $[5000]_{AU}$. The approximately 4x centripetal acceleration boost would produce 2x rotation velocity regardless the mass ratio of wide binary stars. Although the mass ratio of binary stars would affect the rotation radius and rotation velocity by up to factor of 2 between same mass binary stars and the lopsided Sun-Pioneer like interaction system,⁸ this factor does not affect the fact that 4x of the centripetal acceleration would produce 2x of rotation velocity. Therefore, the deviation between the EIDIP framework calculation of 2x rotation velocity booting factor at

⁷ The figure 8 caption of [4]: The upper left panel shows distributions of the median orthogonal deviations (Δ_{\perp}) (defined in Figure 7 of [4]) from 400 MC results with the standard MG-M relation for the main sample of 2463 pure binaries. The upper right panel is with the J-band-based MG-M relation. The bottom panels show distributions of the difference $\delta_{obs-newt} \equiv \langle \Delta_{\perp} \rangle_{obs} - \langle \Delta_{\perp} \rangle_N$. In the lowest acceleration bin at $x_0 \approx -8.0$,

$[5000]_{AU}$ and “the projected velocity boost factor for $s > 5$ kau is measured to be $\gamma_{vp} = 1.20 \pm 0.06 (stat) \pm 0.05 (sys)$ ” of [4] deserve further investigation.

FIG. 9. Total centripetal acceleration ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) to gravity G_N ratio (red line) in linear unit vs distance in log unit for Sun and Pioneer spacecraft system figure

Shown in FIG. 10, at $10^{-10.3}$ centripetal acceleration, the total to Newtonian gravity ratio is $(G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N)/G_N = 10^{1.37}$ which differs from the $\delta_{obs-newt} = 0.122 \pm 0.041$ at $x \approx 10^{-10.3}$ of [4]. Note that the x is a projected centripetal acceleration and Δ_{\perp} is a distance on log-log plane as shown in FIG. 7 are part of causes here.

FIG. 10. Total centripetal acceleration ($G_{APA}^{PSAA} + G_N$) to gravity G_N ratio (red line) vs G_N for Sun and Pioneer spacecraft system figure

$\delta_{obs-newt} = 0$ is naturally satisfied without any adjustment of f_{multi} . The magenta curve in the bottom panels represents the AQUAL prediction for circular orbits with the Milky Way external field.

⁸ Because of the same mass binary stars’ rotation radius is half of lopsided Sun-Pioneer spacecraft rotation radius.

A. EIDIP effects curves overlay on imported figure method

The main goal of the procedure to overlay EIDIP effect curve onto empirical figure used in the EIDIP effect phenomenological tests (EEPT) is to ensure the result is as close as possible to Matlab produced figure with original empirical data. The steps to overlay the EIDIP effects curves on figure 8 of [4] to produce FIG. 8 are:

- (1) Figure 8 of [4], FIG. 5 and FIG. 6 are imported into Visio graphic editing software;
- (2) The curves and inner grides of FIG. 5 are grouped to keep their relationship intact and extracted; Ditto for FIG. 6;
- (3) For the X-axis scaling of both panels: the 10^{-8} and 10^{-11} vertical grid lines (shown by those two purple dotted arrows) are added to assist the alignment with the same grid line on figure 8 of [4], i.e., to ensure the grids on X-axis are aligned between the original figure, the curves from FIG. 5 and FIG. 6;
- (4) For the Y-axis scaling of the upper Δ_{\perp} panel: the grouped Y grids, and the red $\log(G_{APAA}^{PSAA} + G_N)$ and the blue $\log(G_N)$ curves from FIG. 5 are scaled in group such that the blue $\log(G_N)$ sloped line is aligned with the Newtonian gravity line (black) of figure 8 of [4];
- (5) For the Y-axis scaling of the lower panel: the $Y=0$ axis is shifted so that the dotted line (blue line of FIG. 6) at $X=-8$ is aligned with the $Y=0$ location of original figure and keeping Y-unit as is (not scaled).

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this short communication paper, it has explained that the EIDIP framework *predicted* gravitational anomaly near $[2859]_{AU}$ matches the observed WBSA's location, strength, and behaviors. The long-range angular EIDIP effect underlying the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward anomaly (PSAA) would produce gravitational anomaly near $[2859]_{AU}$ with gravity strength $[1.088 \times 10^{-9}]_{ms^{-2}}$ (FIG. 3 and FIG. 4) which aligns with that the observed WBSA occurs at separation approximately larger than $[2000]_{AU}$ and at low acceleration $\leq [10^{-9}]_{ms^{-2}}$. The settle-to-constant of angular EIDIP effect aligns with that the trend of the WBSA's matched well the predictions of ad hoc MOND-type (constant acceleration) modified gravity as discussed in session III and shown in FIG. 8. Furthermore, The long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects underlying the PSAA from other rotational stars can explain the observed external field effect (EFF).

In this vast universe, what is the possibility that the EIDIP framework predicted a gravitational anomaly near $[2859]_{AU}$, and then a gravitational anomaly is observed there *by chance*? On top of the EIDIP framework has 7+ Sigma, that the WBSA can be connected to the PSAA, that the long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects can

be the theoretical base for MOND and MOG models, and that the EIDIP framework has predicted the gravitational anomaly's magnitude and location, these data points affirm that the observed WBSA in Gaia DR3 is real and further strengthen the EIDIP framework 7+ Sigma confidence.

However, some EIDIP framework calculations deviate from the work of [4] (2024), and these deviations deserve further investigation: e.g.,

- (1) The deviation and unit conversion shown in FIG. 8 between the EIDIP effects and the constructed WBSA data shown in figure 8 of [4];
- (2) The assertion that "there is a nearly constant boost of about 40 to 50% in acceleration or 20% boost in relative velocity at separation greater than about 5,000 au" [9] differs from EIDIP framework's calculation shown in FIG. 9;
- (3) The EIDIP framework predicts that the deviation between the log value of $\log_{10}(G_{APAA}^{PSAA} + G_N) - \log_{10}(G_N)$ (dotted blue line) in FIG. 8 will continue to go up instead of turning flat shown as purple line in original figure 8 of [4].

Note that EIDIP effects can also describe the Milky Way rotation curve (MWRC) anomaly without the ad hoc centripetal acceleration $[1.2 \times 10^{-10}]_{ms^{-2}}$ employed by the MOND (slide 23,24 of [1]). Furthermore, some discern readers may wonder why the long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effect underlying the PSAA do not appear to show up in Milk Way rotation curve (MWRC) anomaly phenomenological test. Possible reasons are:

- (1) Analog to the long-range settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects from other rotational stars can explain the observed external field effect (EFF), the EIDIP effects underlying the PSAA and WBSA can appear as external field effect and become part of 'observed' stellar mass (and part of dark matter). I.e., the settle-to-constant angular EIDIP effects could have been included in the stars' mass calculation; hence it is also one of the causes of "dark" matter (slide 25 of [1]).
- (2) The EIDIP effects underlying the MWRC anomaly operates at different energy domain Dx5, which is three order higher than the energy domain Dx2 EIDIP effects underlying the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 sunward acceleration (PSAA) anomaly. Because astronomical EIDIP effects' speed is energy domain dependent at $(32\pi)^{\#}c$ where the # is energy domain rank; e.g., the Dx2 and Dx5 domain's speed is $(32\pi)^2c$ and $(32\pi)^5c$ respectively. With this vast speed difference, the Dx5-domain and Dx2-domain angular EIDIP effects induced gravitational anomaly, especially those induced by turbulent EIDIP effects near singularity as the PSAA and MWRC cases, would not congregate at the same location.

V. REFERENCES

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